

INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. Innovative activity in improving the quality of the education system and scientific innovations, scientific proposals and recommendations on the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.

Keywords: Innovation, education, economics, information and communication, technology.

INTRODUCTION. In the conditions of today's intense competition and economic globalization, issues such as the quality of training of the personnel being trained in the higher education system, increasing their potential and competitiveness are becoming acute problems. On top of that, we should not be limited by opinions that the achieved level of personnel training in the education system of our country, especially in the higher education system, has been recognized in the international arena, we should not stop in the way of further improving its quality aspects, we should raise our work in this regard to a new level. These issues are extremely important today as a result of the situation in the labor market with regard to highly educated personnel, as a result of the measures to be taken to build an innovative economy as a result of the strengthening of international globalization processes.

DISCUSSION. The training of highly qualified and competitive personnel in the higher education system of our country is one of the most important tasks of this system. How effectively this task is solved will have a great impact on achieving the goals of socio-economic reforms and the fundamental reconstruction of the life of our society. Because it is known from practice that the effectiveness of any socio-economic changes directly depends on the professional maturity of the specialists mobilized to perform the tasks set in this regard.

In the independent, democratic Republic of Uzbekistan, the improvement of education, declared as a priority area in the socio-economic, spiritual and cultural development of society, is primarily aimed at achieving its qualitatively new state. This is an extremely complex, complex problem that is being solved in many directions. One of them includes the improvement and reconstruction of the mechanism of management of the educational system, which is a specific form of management of social life. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic

of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 No. PQ-2909 "On measures to further develop the higher education system", No. PQ-3151 dated July 27, 2017 "Measures to further expand the participation of economic sectors and sectors in improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists" on" and decision PQ-3775 of June 5, 2018 on "Increasing the quality of education in higher education institutions and comprehensive additional measures implemented in the country" are of particular importance. In order to improve the economy of our republic and integrate it with the world community, it is necessary to make appropriate use of the scientific potential of our country's higher education institutions. In turn, this issue determines the place of the innovative potential of higher educational institutions in the system of work to be done in terms of conducting innovative and scientific-technical policy implemented at the regional scale. There is a system of ideas, concepts, opinions about the essence of management activity, principles, forms and methods of its cultural implementation. Due to the increasing achievements of mankind in science and technology, economy and social spheres, the demand for knowledge in management activity is also growing continuously. On the one hand, science is interested in the conceptual enrichment of management activities, while on the other hand, practicing managers strive for scientific understanding of their activities and their theoretical justification. Emphasizes the innovative orientation of economic development, the growing need for technological innovation, the principles of organization of innovative activities, and the possibility of clear and appropriate structural-organizational interrelationships. Organization of innovation includes three main aspects:

- an entity that is an association of people who jointly implement the development, implementation and education of innovations in innovative activities;
- the set of actions of the higher education institution aimed at fulfilling the necessary tasks in the innovative activity;
- structures that ensure the internal organization of the system and the improvement of interactions between its elements (departments, departments).

From this point of view, the organization of innovation should be understood as a process of regulating innovative activity, as a subject, firm, institution, innovative enterprise, as organizational structures that determine the composition and position of units and regulate the forms, methods, and processes of innovative activity. Accordingly, innovation management is an extremely complex process. The main factor in the formation of the reputation of a higher education institution in the introduction of innovations depends on the quality of teaching and the quality of educational services. Only the quality educational service provided to the consumer (learner) forms its positive position. Effective management of a higher education institution and formation of a positive image, taking a competitive position in the market of educational services, requires an innovative approach.

The most important factor in the transition to the path of innovative development is not only the development of technical ideas, but also the production of products for domestic and foreign markets, as well as the training of highly qualified experts in the scientific and technical field and high-tech industries in advanced educational institutions for its implementation. is necessary. It should be emphasized that practical mechanisms for the development of scientific-practical research and innovative development and the modernization of production, the implementation of technical and technological renewal processes, ensuring a stronger connection between science and production, and organic cooperation between scientific research organizations and enterprises of real economic sectors establishment of cooperation relations, innovative ideas and projects are the main factors that ensure the quality of education. In our opinion, ensuring the interdependence of education and practice, preparing personnel for practical work, widely introducing scientific achievements to education, ensuring the continuity and integrity of education, independent education are the main principles of developing innovative education in HEIs. At the same time, our goal in the development of innovative education is to combine education and training, to educate intelligence with high moral qualities, and to ensure the high prestige of highly educated specialists in the society. The development of the management system in our university, the wide use of corporate management methods, the modernization of the material and technical base, the effective use of information and communication technologies in the educational process, the introduction of distance education, the regional and international integration of our university, the development of international cooperation in the field of education, and the increase of funding sources progress and the introduction of international standards requirements for the management of the quality of education are promising directions for the development of innovative activities.

In the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, innovative activities in improving the quality of the education system were also mentioned. In the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 (hereinafter referred to as the "Concept"), the higher education system is based on the needs of the social sphere and economic sectors, on the basis of ensuring a solid integration of science, education and production, improving the quality of education, training competitive personnel, scientific and innovative activities. developed for the purpose of effective organization and development of international cooperation, as well as in connection with the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 11, 2019 PQ-4391 "On measures to introduce new principles of management in the system of higher and secondary special education".

The concept defines the strategic goals, priorities, tasks, medium- and long-term stages of the development of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and serves as a basis for the development of programs and complex measures related to the field.

Strategic goals and priorities for the development of the higher education system. The following are the strategic goals of the development of the higher education system:

- increasing the quality of training of highly qualified personnel for the modernization of the country, sustainable socio-economic development, development of human capital based on the requirements of the labor market;

- to increase the level of coverage with higher education, to train highly qualified, creative and systematic thinkers, who can make independent decisions based on international standards, to create the necessary conditions for the manifestation of their intellectual abilities and their formation as spiritually mature individuals;

- to create a healthy competitive environment in the field, to increase its attractiveness, to ensure global competitiveness.

Based on long-term goals, the development of the higher education system is carried out on the basis of the following priorities:

- to expand coverage with higher education, to improve the quality of training of highly educated specialists;

- introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process;

- to increase the efficiency of scientific and research work in higher education institutions, to attract young people to scientific activities, to form an innovative infrastructure of science;

- increasing the effectiveness of spiritual-educational and educational activities; active involvement of personnel customers in the process of training highly qualified specialists;

- ensuring financial independence and stability of higher education institutions, strengthening material and technical support;

- systematic development of higher education institutions and improvement of management activities;

- introduction of effective mechanisms for combating corruption and ensuring transparency;

- to increase the investment attractiveness of the higher education system, to ensure international recognition and competitiveness.

Introducing digital technologies and modern methods to the educational process.

- The following measures will be taken to introduce digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process:

- organization of a system of training highly qualified engineer-technical personnel for the digital economy;

- to ensure the strong integration of modern information and communication technologies and educational technologies, to create additional conditions for the continuous development of the professional skills of pedagogues in this regard;

individualization of educational processes based on digital technologies, development of distance education services, wide implementation of webinar, online, "blended learning", "flipped classroom" technologies;

- organization of distance education programs based on modern information and communication technologies;

-implementation of the "E-MINBAR" platform, which allows online monitoring and mastering of lectures and practical sessions, seminars, as well as uploading them to electronic information storage devices, use of "cloud technologies" in educational processes;

-wide introduction of the electronic library system that allows remote access, expanding the opportunities for students to continuously improve their professional skills by enabling the use of library funds and information bases after completing their studies at a higher education institution;

- to accelerate the creation of national electronic educational resources, to organize the translation of foreign electronic educational resources, to gradually increase the weight of electronic resources in the educational process, to create electronic educational literature, to place information about electronic resources in libraries using QR codes in order to download them to mobile devices create a system;

- creation of an electronic database of scientific and technical information consisting of conference materials, graduation qualification works, master's and doctoral dissertations of the higher educational institution, wide implementation of the anti-plagiarism system in order to ensure the freshness of scientific and technical information in the future;

- developing the use of modern software products that are widely used at the international level in the educational process based on the uniqueness of educational areas and specialties;

- to sharply reduce the number of various reports and data received from higher education institutions, to abandon the paper form of their preparation, to step-by-step transition to the "Electronic University" platform, which ensures the electronification of the management system and educational processes, library and document

circulation, electronic monitoring of the effectiveness of the activities of the participants of the educational process introduction of the system;

- creation of its national system based on the creation of a regularly updated electronic database (Student Record System) that reflects and regularly updates information on teaching staff, bachelor's, master's and doctoral students of higher education institutions;

- with the support of international financial organizations, launching a single information platform of higher education, which incorporates educational-methodical, regulatory and legal documents, statistical data, as well as information on the provision of state interactive services in the field of higher education and is regularly updated - "Higher Education Management Information System" , providing for announcements of vacancies and the possibility of receiving applications online.

he following activities were carried out to increase the effectiveness of scientific and research work in higher education institutions, to widely involve young people in scientific activities, to form the innovative infrastructure of science. is increased:

- step by step implementation of the "University 3.0" concept, which implies the interdependence of education, science, innovation and commercialization of scientific research results in higher education institutions;

- wide attraction of foreign investments, expansion of the scope of paid services and establishment of technoparks, foresights, technology transfer, start-up, accelerator centers in higher education institutions at the expense of other non-budgetary funds, as well as research and forecasting of the socio-economic development of their respective sectors, industries and regions to ensure that they carry out activities on;

- to achieve scientific and innovative activities of professors-teachers, researchers, doctoral students, master's and bachelor's students in technological parks;

- establishment of "spin-off" and "spin-out" enterprises engaged in implementation of scientific research results at higher educational institutions by creating new products and techniques-technologies with high commercialization potential based on extra-budgetary funds, academic entrepreneurship development;

- to ensure the harmonious development of science with advanced achievements based on the analysis of the results of scientific research in the world with the help of the international SsiVal information-analysis system;

- introduction of mechanisms to support the publication of articles in prestigious international scientific journals;

- ensuring the gradual inclusion of scientific journals of higher education institutions in Scopus, ScienceDirect and other international scientific and technical databases;

- development of fundamental, practical and innovative scientific researches, preservation of existing scientific schools and creation of new ones, strengthening of their personnel potential, encouraging the wide involvement of talented young people in science;

by publishing articles in prestigious scientific publications included in the international scientific and technical database, the indicator determining the recognition of the scientific results of their activities at the international level, scientists, professors-teachers and young researchers with a high Hirsh index (h-index) with financial incentives at the expense of extra-budgetary funds introduction of the attendance system;

- raising the quality of scientific research conducted in higher education institutions, creating mechanisms for providing them with statistical, technical and other information, adopting relevant regulatory legal documents in this regard;

-achieving the optimal ratio of the staff of professors and teachers in terms of the age of employees with scientific degrees and titles;

- involving scientists of scientific research institutions in the educational process and scientific leadership, ensuring that scientific works at the stages of master's and doctoral studies are conducted and protected in these scientific research institutions;

- based on the trends of the world scientific research market, specialization of scientific research in each higher education institution (faculty, department and laboratories) in narrow and interdisciplinary fields, adapting them to the needs of production and regional development, defining promising scientific directions with comparative advantage, this increasing the number of highly qualified professors and students in the fields;

- development of international cooperation in the field of science, establishment of active cooperation of leading local higher education institutions with relevant institutes of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan and prestigious foreign higher education and scientific research institutions, making extensive use of the mentoring model;

- speeding up their scientific activity by strictly reducing the number of different magazines and teaching-methodical documents that should be kept by professors-teachers;

ocusing scientific research work on innovative solutions of existing problems in the social sphere and economic sectors, including regional scale, extensive research of problems at the intersection of sciences;

- identifying talented young people, attracting them to academic lyceums, selecting them for higher education institutions, teaching them based on in-depth educational programs, expanding their participation in science Olympiads, increasing their interest in scientific activities, attaching them to qualified specialists who have

achieved high results in the relevant field based on the "mentor-apprentice" system, creation of an electronic data base in this regard;

- establishing and developing cooperation of higher educational institutions with the Youth Academy and the Republican Council on Science and Technology;

- to increase the scientific potential of higher education institutions, to develop the system of training scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel through targeted doctoral studies;

- development of joint degree programs in cooperation with foreign higher education institutions;

- to improve the activities of post-secondary educational institutes based on foreign experience, to coordinate the system of scientific councils and defenses with international experience;

- gradual transfer of the authority to grant scientific degrees and titles to higher education institutions;

- to give freedom to higher education institutions in determining the conditions for admission to doctoral studies, to pay special attention to their scientific achievements in the selection of applicants;

- to create a platform for online observation of meetings of scientific councils awarding scientific degrees from higher education institutions in the regions.

Expected results from the implementation of the concept By fulfilling the tasks set within the framework of the concept, it is envisaged to achieve the following results in the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030:

- on the basis of the development of public-private partnership in the field of higher education, the establishment of the activities of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, including branches of prestigious foreign higher education institutions, the level of coverage with higher education will be higher than 50 percent, a competitive environment will be created in the field;

The National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University will be transformed into the flagship of our country's higher education institutions;

- at least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are included in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1,000 of the rankings of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Nearer Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), including the first place of the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University admission to the list of higher education institutions of 500 places is achieved;

- the educational process in higher education institutions is gradually transferred to the credit-module system;

- on the basis of international experiences, advanced standards of higher education will be introduced, including the step-by-step transition from education focused on acquiring theoretical knowledge to the educational system focused on the formation of practical skills in educational programs;

- the content of higher education will be raised to a new level in terms of quality, a system of highly qualified personnel training will be established, which will make a worthy contribution to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and will find its place in the labor market;

- academic independence of higher education institutions is ensured;

- the "University 3.0" concept, which provides for the interdependence of education, science, innovation and commercialization of the results of scientific research, will be gradually introduced in higher education institutions;

- at the expense of attracting foreign investments, expanding the scope of paid services and other non-budgetary funds, technoparks, foresights, technology transfer, start-up, accelerator centers will be established in higher education institutions, and they will be researching and forecasting the socio-economic development of the relevant industry, sector and regions. - brought to the level of practical institutions;

- it is ensured that professors and teachers of higher education institutions, researchers, doctoral students, bachelor's and master's students publish articles in prestigious international scientific journals with a high impact factor, increase the number of citations to articles, as well as the gradual inclusion of republican scientific journals in the international scientific and technical database ;

-Uzbekistan's higher education system will be transformed into a "hub" implementing international education programs in Central Asia;

- investment attractiveness of higher education will be increased, foreign education and science technologies will be attracted;

- will be developed on the basis of five initiatives, which include comprehensive measures aimed at creating additional conditions for the education of students and youth;

- the infrastructure and material and technical base of higher education institutions will be improved, including by attracting preferential funds from international financial institutions, gradually transferring them to the self-financing system and ensuring financial stability;

- mutually beneficial cooperation of education with production enterprises and scientific-research institutes will be established;

- the level of coverage of higher education will be increased for segments of the population in need of social protection, including persons with disabilities, and infrastructure conditions for them will be improved.

CONCLUSION. In this article, the current state and development of innovative activity in the improvement of the quality of the education system is explained, it describes the essence of the improvement of the quality of the education system, the theoretical basis of the organization of innovative activity, and the current state and development of the effective use of information and communication technology opportunities in the field of information and communication technologies in the educational process. done

The conclusion from the above points is that the improvement of the quality of the educational system according to the direction of its results is divided into innovations as scientific instruments, innovative activities and the educational system.

In order to assess the level of importance of a set of innovations in improving the quality of education, they are divided in this order.

To improve the quality of the educational system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to develop the methodological foundations of the development of innovative activity and the problems of innovation management based on modern requirements.

The effectiveness of innovative activities in improving the quality of the educational system depends on the innovative goals and capabilities of the higher education system, and the innovative thinking skills of employees.

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